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VORTEX DYNAMICS OF SUBSTANCE IN AN ISOLATED SPHEROIDAL VORTEX AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH A CHARGE

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Abstract

The given work is devoted to the study of vortex processes flowing in the liquid spheroidal vortex leading to appearance of fluxes of a substance, which are responsible for appearance of characteristics (potential and intensities of fields) in space surrounding it. In this work we are developing further the proposed by us new physical conception about a vortical state of a substance in the form of a viscous liquid self-closed spheroidal vortex, that allows us to take a new look at the problems of the existence of different kind of fields of interaction and we elaborate new dynamical theory of emission giving the possibility to have a new look at many processes occurring in Nature. The mechanism of vortex interaction of an emitted matter with the substance in the vortex is also considered.

Keywords: charge, spheroidal vortex, emission, vortex dynamics of substance, circulation, intensity of vortex, vortex interactions, electromagnetism.

1. Introduction

Abdus Salam in 1980 [1] identified the fundamental problem of revealing the essence of the physical existence of charges and their role in interactions. We know that each type of interaction is associated with a certain parameter of the object. In the case of gravitational interactions the mass m of a body is said to be the basis parameter of interacting bodies. The charge Q is being the main parameter, coming out as a means of the main quantity at electrostatic, magnetic and electromagnetic interactions. The reasons of difference of main parameters of separate kinds of interactions are not clear up to now. There are not clear notions about physical essence of a charge and mechanism of its appearing on the surfaces of interacting objects. The elaboration of the concept of the charge stopped on the statement of the fact that it exists in two kinds - positive and negative.

This work is devoted to the consideration of the vortex nature of the charge in various types of interactions, as well as the causes and mechanism of its manifestation in interacting bodies. The analysis showed that each atom of an interacting object should be considered as a "ball-drop" filled with a substance that has its own mass, volume and radius. We will assume that such "balls" have the ability to deform and rotate

around their own axis, which is very important for determining the nature of the vortex motion during interaction.

The vortex state of a substance was found by Oersted [2] in 1820, but this fact remained incomprehensible and it is not realized up to now.

Taking into account of the fact found by Oersted in 1820 the simultaneous consideration of equations of forces of interactions by different kinds of interactions - Newton's law for the gravitational interactions, Coulomb's laws for electrostatic and magnetic interactions and also the law for interacting of two currents allows us to determine that all specified kinds of interactions can be led to the united hydrodynamic model while the quantity comes out as a basis of a charge being the main parameter of all kinds of interactions

$$Q = \sqrt{mv^2r} \quad (1)$$

where m is a mass of a substance making up the body of a vortex, v is a velocity of rotation of the mass around own axis, r is the radius of the vortex.

By this, as it is shown from Eq. (1), the velocity of its rotation about own axis contributes to the quantity of a charge for the same mass.

Deducing in Eq. (1) the meaning of area from under the sign of root and taking into account that $Q = \Phi = \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{S}$, where Φ is the magnetic flux with the dimension $[M^{1/2} L^{3/2} T^{-1}]$, we get new expression not only of a charge

$$Q = r^2 \sqrt{\rho v^2}, \quad (2)$$

but of magnetic induction

$$B = \sqrt{\rho v^2}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is a density of a substance of a vortex, v is a velocity of its rotating around own axis, r is a radius of the vortex. The quantity ρv^2 , standing under the root sign, is being nothing more nor less than a double dynamic or impact pressure [3-4], calculated by a parametric value of the velocity or, in other words, it is a unit element of volume of a substance of the spheroidal vortex. In another way, the expressions (2) and (3) show that the charge presents itself the particles – the units of the volume of a substance of the vortex forming the magnetic induction B , creating the dynamic pressure. As it is known that $\text{div } \mathbf{B} = 0$, this fact tells that the same rotating mass of a substance creates the flux Ψ_s of particles of a substance for appearing of the magnetic induction.

On the other hand, if the expression (1) for charge will be presented in the form

$$Q = \sqrt{v(mvr)} \quad (4)$$

It can be seen that the charge presents itself nothing but the fluxes of mass possessing the action (the fluxes of masses bearing the action).

Thus, the charge is the fluxes - the jets of particles – the units of volumes of a substance, possessing the kinetic energy, transferring the action, bearing the angular momentums, outflowing as in polar, so in radial directions by different kinds of interactions.

Namely these fluxes of particles emitted by the body outside the limit of its volume that create these

characteristics which are accepted be called potentials and intensities of fields, responsible for the interaction between bodies. It is the presence of these particles that makes it possible to consider all kinds of interactions from unified positions [3-5].

On the basis of the obtained expression for a charge the gravitational charges Q_G of atoms of the chemical elements of the Periodic Table of Elements of D.I.Mendeleev [5], the values of velocities (v) of motion of a substance in atoms (Table 1) and the values of circulation of the velocity of transfer of a substance $\Gamma_{rot} = (v \cdot r)$ in them (Table 2) [4-6]. It is found that of one of basic characteristics of atoms is being the circulation ($v \cdot r$) of a velocity of transfer of a substance in its volume except mass (Table 2). As it is seen from Table 2, the circulation of a velocity of transfer of a substance in atoms within the period remains constant. Some distinctions in value by period, seemingly, connected with an accuracy of definition of an effective radius of an atom. In the whole, the jump-like change of the velocity of circulation of a substance approximately on average by the same value

$\Delta(v \cdot r) \approx [10.7 \pm (0.81 \div 1.5)] \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is observed from period to period, remaining a constant value within the period. Table shows also that we should separate the noble gases out into special, Zero, group and to put them at the beginning of a following period. Because of it that the circulation of a velocity of transfer of a substance of this period of elements essentially differs from the circulation of that period, to which they are concerned in present time.

Table 1

Velocities of motion of a substance $v \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ in atoms of elements [5-6]

period	group										
	0	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII		
1		H ¹ 4.93									
2	He ² 5.53	Li ³ 7.04	Be ⁴ 9.45	B ⁵ 11.06	C ⁶ 13.70	N ⁷ 13.94	O ⁸ 17.20	F ⁹ 18.14			
3	Ne ¹⁰ 11.82	Na ¹¹ 11.58	Mg ¹² 12.98	Al ¹³ 14.47	Si ¹⁴ 15.02	P ¹⁵ 16.28	S ¹⁶ 18.49	Cl ¹⁷ 19.93			
4a	Ar ¹⁸ 15.19	K ¹⁹ 13.58	Ca ²⁰ 15.02	Sc ²¹ 17.54	Ti ²² 19.00	V ²³ 20.53	Cr ²⁴ 21.23	Mn ²⁵ 21.91	Fe ²⁶ 22.53	Co ²⁷ 23.24	Ni ²⁸ 23.29
4b		²⁹ Cu 23.46	³⁰ Zn 23.62	³¹ Ga 23.50	³² Ge 23.65	³³ As 25.89	³⁴ Se 27.36	³⁵ Br 28.25			
5a	Kr ³⁶ 21.67	Rb ³⁷ 19.55	Sr ³⁸ 21.26	Y ³⁹ 23.41	Zr ⁴⁰ 25.14	Nb ⁴¹ 26.57	Mo ⁴² 27.67	Tc ⁴³ 28.41	Ru ⁴⁴ 29.36	Rh ⁴⁵ 29.63	Pd ⁴⁶ 29.79
5b		⁴⁷ Ag 28.83	⁴⁸ Cd 28.74	⁴⁹ In 28.39	⁵⁰ Sn 30.34	⁵¹ Sb 30.52	⁵² Te 31.68	⁵³ I 32.17			
6a	Xe ⁵⁴ 25.84	Cs ⁵⁵ 23.49	Ba ⁵⁶ 26.19	La ⁵⁷ 28.70	Hf ⁷² 35.28	Ta ⁷³ 38.12	W ⁷⁴ 38.30	Re ⁷⁵ 38.82	Os ⁷⁶ 40.73	Ir ⁷⁷ 40.79	Pt ⁷⁸ 39.45
6b		⁷⁹ Au 38.95	⁸⁰ Hg 39.70	⁸¹ Tl 37.63	⁸² Pb 36.76	⁸³ Bi 41.57	⁸⁴ Po 40.65	⁸⁵ At -			
7	Rn ⁸⁶	Fr ⁸⁷ 29.72	Ra ⁸⁸ 32.66	Ac ⁸⁹ 35.22	Ku ¹⁰⁴						

Table 2

The circulation of velocity of transfer of a mass $(v \cdot r) \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in atoms of Periodic Table of D.I.Mendeleev [3, 5-6]

Group Period	v · r middle	0	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII		
1			H ¹ 2.27									
2	10.74	He ² 8.02	Li ³ 10.92	Be ⁴ 10.58	B ⁵ 10.84	C ⁶ 9.73	N ⁷ 11.15	O ⁸ 10.32	F ⁹ 11.61			
3	20.59	Ne ¹⁰ 18.92	Na ¹¹ 22.01	Mg ¹² 20.77	Al ¹³ 20.69	Si ¹⁴ 20.73	P ¹⁵ 20.97	S ¹⁶ 19.23	Cl ¹⁷ 19.73			
4a	29.83	Ar ¹⁸ 29.17	K ¹⁹ 31.92	Ca ²⁰ 29.59	Sc ²¹ 28.42	Ti ²² 27.94	V ²³ 27.51	Cr ²⁴ 27.17	Mn ²⁵ 27.82	Fe ²⁶ 27.49	Co ²⁷ 28.12	Ni ²⁸ 27.95
4b			²⁹ Cu 30.03	³⁰ Zn 30.7	³¹ Ga 32.90	³² Ge 34.05	³³ As 32.1	³⁴ Se 32.01	³⁵ Br 31.36			
5a	42.03	Kr ³⁶ 42.9	Rb ³⁷ 48.48	Sr ³⁸ 45.71	Y ³⁹ 42.13	Zr ⁴⁰ 40.23	Nb ⁴¹ 38.79	Mo ⁴² 38.46	Tc ⁴³ 38.64	Ru ⁴⁴ 38.17	Rh ⁴⁵ 38.52	Pd ⁴⁶ 39.62
5b			⁴⁷ Ag 41.51	⁴⁸ Cd 43.39	⁴⁹ In 44.86	⁵⁰ Sn 43.39	⁵¹ Sb 44.25	⁵² Te 44.67	⁵³ I 43.75			
6a	53.54	Xe ⁵⁴ 56.34	Cs ⁵⁵ 62.73	Ba ⁵⁶ 58.15	La ⁵⁷ 53.67	Hf ⁷² 56.10	Ta ⁷³ 54.13	W ⁷⁴ 53.24	Re ⁷⁵ 53.19	Os ⁷⁶ 53.36	Ir ⁷⁷ 53.84	Pt ⁷⁸ 54.84
6b			⁷⁹ Au 56.09	⁸⁰ Hg 57.96	⁸¹ Tl 60.22	⁸² Pb 62.50	⁸³ Bi 62.77	⁸⁴ Po 57.31	⁸⁵ At			
7		Rn ⁸⁶	Fr ⁸⁷ 83.22	Ra ⁸⁸ 76.75	Ac ⁸⁹ 71.49	Ku ¹⁰⁴						

2. The mechanism for the formation of vortex flows of matter that forms the outer shell - the “locking layer” of a spheroidal vortex.

The found expression of charge Q allows us to develop the hydrodynamic model of mechanisms of appearing of fluxes of a substance, creating the charge. We will examine it in more detail, qualitatively tracking the change of an internal structure (morphology) of an isolated rotating liquid drop of a substance of an atom placed in vacuum. Practically it is being under action of only forces of a surface tension and by virtue of the fact that in the given case only the spheroid pos-

sesses the minimal surface, the drop will have the spheroidal shape, i.e. we will examine the rotating vortex having equal density of a substance.

What is the picture of flows of a substance in the vortex? There is not a direct answer to it and we cannot just make a study of the picture of flows of liquid in the vortex of such size as a nucleus, we will look for analogies. As any vortex, in its central part near axis of rotation the “spheroidal” rotating vortex will have a funnel similar one which is in the cavitation bubble (vortex), created in a liquid by irradiating it with ultrasound (Pic. 1).

Pic 1. An one-pole spheroidal vortex (our model).

However, the vortex is filled up with the substance, thus, the internal conic vortex cannot extend over its limits and finishes somewhere within its center. The general picture of current of a liquid in the central conic axial vortex will be analogous to the picture of motion of a liquid in the centrifugal sprayer - the device supplied the outlet of a liquid jet of a flux not only at the axial component of a velocity, but also at radial one, i.e. the liquid flows along the helical lines similar to the vortex, formed in the outflow tube in the bath. The flux getting from the widest part of the vortex tube of the vortex into the narrow cone is speeding up - the equation of the flow rate works:

$$\rho \cdot v_{n1} \cdot S_1 = \rho \cdot v_{n2} \cdot S_2 = Const, \quad (5)$$

where ρ is a density of a substance, v_n is a translational velocity, S is an area of a cross-section.

The intensity of the vortex cone is expressed by the equation

$$\kappa_S = \Gamma_\xi * \Gamma_\rho = \left(\frac{2\psi_B}{\rho}\right) * \Gamma_\rho, \quad (6)$$

where you can see the mutual connection between the circulation of the vorticity of the vortex and the circulation of transfer of velocity of a substance in spheroidal vortex. Here, in Eq. (6) the “interaction” between two different circulations Γ_ξ and Γ_ρ follows from the law of conservation of the double mapping of circulation on a straight line, according to the remark of the Norwegian scientist Sophus Lie (our interpretation). According to this equation and the law of conservation

of angular momentum, as the radius of the vortex tube decreases, the tangential velocity also increases inversely proportional to it, i.e. rotation speeds up.

The law of invariability of angular momentum for the spheroidal vortex, the product of the rotation speed v_{rot} by radius R according to Helmholtz's second law remains constant from one jet to another, it may be written down as applied to it

$$v_R \cdot R = v_r \cdot r = Const, \quad (7)$$

The radius of the central vortex filament is small close by the center of the spherical vortex, but the velocity of rotation of a liquid is big. Bernoulli's equation, connecting the parameters of a jet flowing through a conic central vortex in various cross-section areas will look like this [3-5]:

$$P + \frac{\rho v^2}{2} = P + \rho \frac{(v_t^2 + v_{rot}^2)}{2} = P_S = Const, \quad (8)$$

In this equation the kinetic energy of a liquid adds up from the energy of a translational motion with velocity v_t and the energy of a rotational motion with velocity v_{rot} in the complex motion through a cone of the vortex. The specific kinetic energy $\rho v^2/2$ by analogy

with the first term P is called a high-speed or dynamic pressure - this energy may turn into pressure at a delay of motion.

It is seen from Eq. (8), that the pressure and velocity in the vortex are "antagonists" and obey the dependence relation

$$P \sim 1/v_{rot} \sim 1/r, \quad (9)$$

If along a flux the velocity v_{rot} rises, then the pressure P drops and on the contrary with slowing down of the flux the pressure is raised. With increasing the speed of rotation v_{rot} in the narrow part of the vortex cone the pressure inside it is reduced and, the liquid surrounding the end of funnel is intensively drawn into the canal of a vortex funnel, rising along its walls, forming the counter vortex flux. Hence, the main vortex induces the appearance of the second equivalent vortex, and this leads to the situation, that in the axial part of the rotating spherical vortex two vortex cones directed towards each other, formed by separate vortical fluxes of a substance, sliding one beside another and having the different direction of rotation, are created (Pic. 2).

Fig. 2. a) A spheroidal vortex with two opposite poles;
b) the model of a spheroidal vortex with two opposite poles.

If the direction of rotation of the spheroidal vortex corresponding to the rule of the right screw is taken as the main direction of rotation, then the second cone in relation to the first one, which inherits the rotation inherent in the spheroidal vortex itself, will have left-sided rotation. (Pic. 2b, 3). Here, the chiral nature of the vortex is manifested by its internal rotation - confirmation of the existence of the dualistic nature of vortex dynamics of the spheroidal vortex itself [7-8].

Thus, by rotating of the spheroidal vortex here inside it the axial vortex cavity - the core is created, of which along walls two oppositely directed fluxes move. There are these two flows flowing out from the axial regions of the vortex that create two different poles, which we observe at the magnet; in this case, the matter flowing out from one of the cones is being the antimatter in relation to matter flowing out from the other cone. A more detailed description of the vortex structure of the vortex core was given in the works [3-4, 8].

The liquid caught in the vortex funnel, experiencing the accelerating spiral twisting, tends to break away through a narrow nozzle of a funnel outside. Centrifugal forces at the outlet in the region of the critical cross-section, situated in the center of the spherical vortex, form not just another vortex funnel from a flowing out high-speed jet of a liquid. The configuration of another (second) funnel reminds of a socket (bell-like) of one-sheeted hyperboloid [9] (Pic. 5). The speed of rotation and the translational velocity of motion are maximums

in the central part of the spheroidal vortex and they noticeable weaken toward its periphery. Here the stream gets broken into separate lines of the current. They form lines of a liquid hyperboloid that create, in their turn, the "flame" of spraying of a substance into separate drops just as how it is going on in a flame of spraying of a centrifugal sprayer in jet engines.

By this, every drop of this jet in this case represents itself the microvortex - magneton. Exactly these microvortices possessing the azimuthal rotation that are responsible for a magnetic rotation of a plane of polarization of light, discovered by M. Faraday in 1845 and which got in science the name of Faraday's effect. Therefore J.C.I. Maxwell had been right when he said, "the discovery of a magnetic rotation of the plane of polarization of light although it did not lead to equally important practical applications, as some of earlier discoveries by Faraday, had for a science the greatest value as it gave the thorough dynamical proof of the fact that wherever there exist the magnetic forces, there is matter, small particles of which rotate around the axes parallel to the direction of this force" [10].

Precisely these jets of matter that create meridional flows of matter are responsible for the magnetic fields not only of separate particles, but also of planets, stars and other objects of the Universe. They also create the surface tension of a liquid spheroidal vortex.

3. Determination of circulation of the general nature of periodic motions of separated jet vortex flows (filaments) carrying a charge Q.

The same rotating particles of liquid, microvortices, flying out of the spray cone, due to the Magnus effect, create those closed solenoidal jets of matter - vortex filaments, characteristic of the magnetic fields of permanent magnets (Pic. 3, 4).

$$\Psi_S = \frac{\rho \kappa}{2\Gamma}, \tag{10}$$

where κ is the intensity of the vortex, penetrating its cross section, ρ is a density, Γ – the circulation of the vortex filament [3-6].

At each point of the vortex filament of the outer shell of the spheroidal vortex (red lines on Pic. 3) the total sum of the two flows is

$$\vec{\Psi}_B = \vec{\Psi}_r + \vec{\Psi}_\perp = \frac{\rho}{2}(\vec{v}_r + \vec{v}_\xi) \tag{11}$$

It is shown that the value of the circulation of vortex filaments Γ is directly related to the magnitude of the “vertical” vorticity ζ of the spheroidal vortex itself rotating around its own axis with a speed v , where the vorticity ζ in Cartesian coordinates is written as

$$\zeta = \vec{k} \cdot \nabla \times \vec{v} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \tag{12}$$

And considering that here is hidden the special case of description of the vorticity of a vortex filament particle written in its natural coordinates, where the value $v\kappa_S$ is known as a vorticity twist (curling) at an angle φ according to the law of a curvature vorticity:

$$\zeta_{MP} = v\kappa_S - \partial v / \partial n \tag{13}$$

Thus, for the axisymmetric motion of an incompressible vortex filament, we will have an equation for circulation

$$u_x \frac{\partial \Gamma_\varphi}{\partial x} + u_r \frac{\partial \Gamma_\varphi}{\partial r} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_\varphi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma_\varphi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Gamma_\varphi}{\partial r} \right), \tag{14}$$

taking into account that $\Gamma_\varphi = Const$, then the solution of this equation leads to the law of change in the specific moment of the microvortex-particle, which is being an element of the vortex filament.

Taking into account the internal rotation of the element of the vortex filament, the law of the total change in the angular momentum of the particle

$$\rho \int ([\vec{x} \times \vec{v}] + \vec{\xi}) dV = \int p[\vec{n} \times \vec{x}] dS \tag{15}$$

(where V is the microvortex volume, S is the microvortex cross section, \vec{n} is a normal to the surface) makes a total contribution to the change in the value $\vec{\Psi}_B$

Pic. 3. A spheroidal vortex rotating around its own axis with a right shift (red) and a left shift (blue). [3, 8-9]

4. The mechanism of formation of radial flows of matter in a spheroidal vortex.

How does the source of fluxes of a liquid, moving in radial directions, appear in the center of the rotating spheroidal vortex?

In order to answer to this question we return to the axial conical vortex ending in the center of our rotating spheroidal vortex. The radius of the vortex on the spike of the vortex cone is very small and the speed of rotation is very big. By approaching to the center of the vortex the radius of the vortex cone $r_{cone} \rightarrow 0$, and, according to equations of conversation of angular momentum (7) and Bernoulli's equation (8) the speed of rotation tends $v_{rot} \rightarrow \infty$, and the pressure $P \rightarrow -\infty$. The mathematics leads to contradiction with physics "to an impossible result": - the appearance of an infinitely largest velocity and an infinitely great and also negative pressure.

Pic. 4.

This cannot be, consequently the picture of phenomenon itself is changed, and a sharp change of a stream occurs. As it is well known, at passing the current, in the equation for the force of interacting currents the coefficient, equal to the speed of light c and absent in other equations for forces of interactions, is appearing (Table 1 and 2 in [3-4]). And that coefficient is related to the radial symmetry of an electrical field appearing by passing the current. This fact allows one to say that, when at passing the electric current through an atom, the tangential velocity at the end of a vortex cones reaches the velocity, equal to the speed of light, while the ends of vortex cones become instable. From them the substance begins to break away and in the center of the spheroidal rotating vortex there appears the source of high-speed, high-temperature jets of a substance, moving in radial direction. Moreover, every cone creates the fluxes in an opposite hemisphere (Pic. 2a, 4, 5).

This description is not a fantasy, because, every of us, switching on the electrical lighting in any room, observes such a picture repeatedly and constantly. When the electric current starts to flow along spiral of the electric lamp, of which its atoms are components, being in the gravitational state before that, so they suddenly start to emit the photons to all directions forming in their interiors and flying away with the speed of light.

Pic. 5

The jet breaking out from the "nozzle" of a cone, inheriting from it the vortex motion, at first behaves as a twisted flooded jet. By this, these ends of the vortex cone, passing through the viscous substance of the vortex, by virtue of the great velocities of circulation of a substance they lose the velocity of the azimuthal rotation and, already at some distance away from the center – the "nozzle" the twisted jet behaves as not twisted. Thus, the convection of a substance of the vortex occurs from its central part to periphery [8-9].

The matter broken away from the cones of rotation, moving in radial direction, has a range of velocities, that, in its turn, leads to a certain spectrum of matter fluxes, possessing various velocities of motion from $v_{Gr} < v \leq c$ (where v_{Gr} is own velocity of rotation of the spheroidal vortex around its axis in a gravitational state), i.e. up to fluxes, possessing velocities equal to the speed of light at the yield from the spheroidal vortex. The part of these hot and high-speed flows - bunches of a substance, having reached colder layers of the vortex, losing the part of their energy, runs along a layer at the velocity equal to their velocity of motion.

Pic. 6

Such a "blocking" stable layer slows down and eventually may stop the motion of the part of the liquid flows, which come to this layer from the central region. The head parts of the infiltrated flux of a substance start to spread along the layer. These jets are similar mushroom thermics floating on from a warmed surface (Pic. 6, 7).

It is not difficult to imagine such a situation, when the spectrum of velocities, emitted by a vortex cone of matter, creates in the body of the spheroidal vortex the stratified shells, between which the convection goes on (Pic. 7).

Pic. 7

The fluxes of a substance of the internal central part of a jet, having a velocity of motion above the velocity of motion of the "blocking" layer, continue their movement to boundaries of the rotating "sphere" itself, after reaching which on its surface they create the hexagonal cells with radial fluxes from the center of the cell to periphery like those, which are characteristic not only for Benard convection, but also arise in "magnetic liquid", situated in the orthogonal field [8-9] and they are well observed on the Solar surface.

The motion of a substance does not be closed at the boundary of the body. The head parts of the fluxes, forming the convective cell, gathered the high velocities of a translational motion in radial direction, come off from the body of the vortex and turn out in the space far from its surface. However, they themselves introduce the fluxes of particles, creating magnetic force lines inherited from the central axial part of the vortex that they cannot be closed at the body of the vortex. Because of this, by its vortex nature ($\text{div } \mathbf{B} = 0$) and according to Helmholtz's third law for the vortex motion they are closed on themselves.

Pic. 8.

Thus, in space close to the body of the vortex the dynamical structure – the convective cell - the photon like the observed smoke rings (by shape they remind of the convective cell) appears (Pic. 8). In contrast to the convective cell the volumetric frame of the photon is created by meridional magnetic force lines. In the case, if the convective cell flowing out takes away the part of the mass of the central vortex, so as a basis of elements of radiation here the atoms, ions, protons, electrons or other elementary particles may appear, but in contrary to the photon they possess the azimuthal rotation around their own axes already [3, 9].

Every separate part of radially moving particles, having minor azimuthal rotation, will move to their "blocking layer" which is formed at the cost of the spectrum of fluxes of particles creating shells from magnetic force lines around the vortex and which serve for them original "reflecting Heaviside's layers". Losing their own energy and reflecting from them, they begin to turn back. The descending jets of a substance, losing energy and reflecting from their "blocking layers", create those forces (or that pressure), which are responsible for one of mechanisms of attraction both in gravitational

and electromagnetic interactions (Pic. 7, 9), i.e. in the given case the attraction due to outflow of a substance is a convergence:

$$\operatorname{con} \mathbf{E} = -\operatorname{div} \mathbf{E} = -\operatorname{div} \left(\frac{Q}{R^2} \right) = -\operatorname{div} \left(\frac{r^2 \sqrt{\rho v^2}}{R^2} \right) \quad (16)$$

The convergence was created by jets of returning particles, flown out beyond the limits of the spherical vortex and having velocities in a range from $v_{\text{spheroid}} < v \leq c$.

Pic. 9. The reflecting layers of Heaviside

Another mechanism of attraction lies hidden in the mechanism itself of interaction of the microvortex with an object, into which the microvortex penetrates at interaction. As regards kinematics of the motion of the microvortex itself in the body of vortex, that it cannot be fixed because of exceedingly high velocity of its motion. However, if consider the data of the experiments of O.Reynolds, investigated in 1876 the resistance of the vortex rings to the motion, who had noticed that they move without resistance, keeping by this own primary impulse [11]. Thus, it is possible to conclude that the microvortex has the mechanism of the motion that is inherent only to it. It lies in that the disturbances produced by the circulation of a substance along the outer shell of the microvortex do not change the structure of that medium, in which the microvortex moves, i.e. when moving not all volume enclosed by the convective cell is transferred, but only the outer shell of the microvortex itself, having a convective structure, is transferred. Moving at the same velocity as the substance in its magnet force lines the microvortex as if it rolled along the line of its motion throwing its substance forward. Its separate jets forming meridional magnetic force lines pass through the medium not changing their primary impulse in this case and, if the microvortex does not enter into the resonance with the medium, through which it passes, thus, if the microvortex is not absorbed by the medium that it passes through one. And, the microvortex having gone out through it that by its return streams, as if it pushed slightly the interacting object in a direction of the object, which emitted it. In this case, it is the line of interaction that is the line of the Least Action fits the straight connecting the interacting objects and that is being the trajectory of motion of the microvortex itself.

5. Conclusions

Thus, all of the above allows us to conclude that:

- different masses of matter in the Universe are characterized by a vortex state;
- in Nature there a single mechanism of vortex interaction exists;
- the vortex mechanism of motion, the nonlinear interaction of meridional flows of matter and azimuthal rotational motions, as well as the direct action of the azimuthal rotation of a spheroidal vortex form the basis

of the mechanism for converting the kinetic (mechanical) energy of the vortex central filament into magnetic, electrical and gravitational energy of a spheroidal vortex, i.e. it is being the basis of all physical phenomena observed in Nature;

- the main difference in the strength of interactions is due to the speed of rotation of the interacting objects themselves.

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